

THERMAL ISOLATION TECHNIQUES FOR CURE MONITORING USING FBG OPTICAL SENSORS

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SUMMARY

This paper reports on experimental thermal isolation techniques for Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors used for the cure monitoring of thermoset composites. A numerical model for the FBG is introduced. This study is primarily focused on prepreg materials used in the wind energy industry.

Keywords: FBG sensors, cure monitoring, residual stresses and processing, resistance network.

INTRODUCTION

Cure monitoring can improve the efficiency of processing as it can identify critical points in the cure reaction such as the required degree of cross linking for termination of the cure cycle. Therefore, the production time for the product can be reduced and optimised without danger of producing incorrectly cured material.

Fibre optic strain sensors have mainly been applied to composite materials for structural health monitoring in the aerospace and wind energy industry. The physical size of an FBG optical fibre is extremely small (260 μ m) compared with traditional strain measuring systems, which enables it to be embedded into composite structures for determining the strain distributions with minimal affect on the mechanical properties of the host material (Figure 1a).

The FBG sensor is formed of three component materials; a core, glass cladding and protective coating (Figure 1b). The mechanical properties of the cladding and core are the same, although the reflective index of the core is slightly higher in order to satisfy Snell's law. The protective coating is made from an acrylate or polyimide material and provides shielding against moisture absorption and damage. In the case of embedded optical fibres, it is generally accepted that polyimide coating provides a better adhesion to the host composite material than the standard telecommunication acrylate coating [1] and a higher interfacial strength [2].

The FBG sensor is a periodic modulation in the core of an optical fibre. The centre wavelength of the light reflected from a Bragg grating is dependent on the refractive index of the core and the periodicity of the Bragg grating. FBG sensors are sensitive to temperature change which affects both the refractive index and the periodicity of the grating.

Figure 1 (a) SEM image of a sectional view of a polyimide coated FBG sensor in an E-glass composite. (b) Single model fibre.

Hence, it is essential to devise a method for eliminating the affect of temperature. The relationship between the refractive Bragg wavelength shift ($\Delta\lambda_B$) corresponding to the change of strain and temperature at the grating region (ϵ_g) can be expressed as

$$\Delta\lambda_B/\lambda_B = K\Delta\epsilon_g + \beta\Delta T \quad (1)$$

Where

$\beta = (\alpha_{CTE} - \alpha_n)$ = Temperature sensitive factor

α_{CTE} = coefficients of thermal expansion of the optical fibre

α_n = thermo-optic coefficient

K = strain-optic coefficient.

Thermosetting resins generally shrink during cure in the order of 1 to 8% [3], depending on the resin chemistry, which introduces internal strain into the laminate. It is the monitoring of this strain which provides information on the degree of cure of the resin and provides an opportunity to feedback internal cure strain data into the FE design stage of the component. The challenge in utilising FBG sensors for the purpose of cure strain monitoring is to accurately isolate thermal fluctuations from the true strain induced by chemical resin shrinkage and thermal contraction. Understanding processing conditions and the internal curing strain of thermoset composite structures is an important step in the understanding processing and material development and structural optimisation. The research reported here aims to investigate experimental methods of isolating thermal influences on FBG's when embedded within a curing thermoset composite laminate.

Published research on the use of fibre optic sensors for cure monitoring of composites is limited and tends to focus on transmission spectroscopy, evanescent wave spectroscopy and refractive index monitoring [4]. The use of fibre optics for temperature monitoring of curing laminates has been reported with some success using high birefringence fibres [5], where the transverse strain developed during the cure process of a glass fibre/epoxy resin was detected. However, these optic sensors are not commercially available.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The sensors used in each experiment consisted of FBGs with a grating length of 25mm written onto a polyimide coated Single Mode fibre. The wavelength shift was recorded using an Insensys three channel OEM-1030 fibre sensor interrogator unit and temperature was recorded using NI hardware and Labview software at an acquisition frequency of 1 Hz. All heating and curing was done on a flat aluminium tool using a silicon mat heater and PID controller. Thermal error of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ was recorded for the process described.

Comparison of different isolated capillary tubes

Three different capillary tubes were studied as a strain isolation media based on their co-efficient of thermal expansion, conductivity and relative diameter to the fibre optic (Table 1). FBG sensors were encased in the capillary tubes and then sealed at both ends using a rapid curing epoxy. The isolated FBG's were then placed on top of the heating tool with a reference FBG sensor (unprotected) and a K type thermocouple. A light felt based insulating cover was then placed on top to help retain the heat. The fibres were then heated at varying heating rates of 0.5, 1 and $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ (from 25°C to 100°C).

Table 1: Geometry of the isolation material

Isolation material	Inner Diameter (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Length (mm)
Stainless steel 16 gauge	1.200	0.225	80
Stainless steel 25 gauge	0.305	0.128	80
Glass capillary tube	0.300	0.050	80

Figure 2 cross-sectional view of an isolation material.

The glass capillary tubing showed minimal sensitivity to changes in heating rate relative to the reference sensor (Figure 3). A sinusoidal fluctuation was observed for all sample rates of between $-30\mu\epsilon$ & $-5\mu\epsilon$ after the first 15mins. At heating rates of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ or above, neither stainless steel capillary tubes tested would be suitable as a strain isolation system due to the residual strain observed. Based on the low thermal lag and matched coefficient of thermal expansion observed in these tests, the glass capillary tubing was used to isolate the strain effects from the FBG when embedded within a curing prepreg laminate.

Figure 3 Differences in strain between each FBG sensor isolation material and reference sensor at a heating rate of 2°C/min

Isolation of thermal effects from chemical shrinkage

Unidirectional plaques were moulded from two plies of heavyweight UD1600gsm wind energy grade prepreg. Two parallel FBGs (one isolated from curing strain by a glass tube) were moulded in the centre of each plaque, and two plaques were made; one where the FBG sensors were aligned (0°) with the reinforcement axis and the second, where the FBG was perpendicular (90°) to the reinforcement axis. The resulting laminate was consolidated using a conventional vacuum bag process at 95% vacuum pressure, with a cure schedule as per manufacturer’s guidelines

NUMERICAL MODELLING

Figure 4: (a) Cross-sectional view of FBGs layers in isolation material (b) Simplified 1D thermal resistances network

The heat flow is simplified to an axysymmetric, 1-D thermal resistances network as seen in Figure 4(b) and the heat loss from each cylindrical layer is shown below:

The heat transfer from outer surface of isolation material to mid section of isolation material can be expressed as:

$$\dot{q}_{1-2} = \frac{(T_1 - T_2)}{\sum R_2} = M_2 C_2 \dot{T}_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\sum R_2 = R_{Conv(PR-IS)} + R_{Cond(IS)} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{2D_{Out_IS}}{r_{Out_IS}}\right)}{2\pi h_{PR-IS} L} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_{Out_IS}}{r_{mid_IS}}\right)}{2\pi k_{IS} L} \quad (3)$$

Heat transfer from mid-section of isolation material to mid-section of air region:

$$\dot{q}_{2-3} = \frac{(T_2 - T_3)}{\sum R_3} = M_3 C_3 \dot{T}_3 \quad (4)$$

$$\sum R_3 = R_{Cond(IS)} + R_{Conv(IS-Air)} + R_{Cond(Air)}$$

$$\sum R_3 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_{mid_IS}}{r_{in_IS}}\right)}{2\pi k_{IS} L} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{2D_{in_IS}}{r_{in_IS}}\right)}{2\pi h_{IS-Air} L} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_{Out_Air}}{r_{mid_Air}}\right)}{2\pi k_{Air} L} \quad (5)$$

The equations for the heat transfer from outer surface of isolation material to mid section of isolation material follow the same form as (4) and (5).

The isolation material has good bonded characteristics to the protective coating so we can assume equilibrium condition between the layers:

$$\varepsilon_{IS} = \varepsilon_{PC} = \varepsilon_{GC} = \varepsilon_{Core}$$

$$\varepsilon_{IS} = \frac{\Delta L}{L} = \frac{F_{IS}}{A_{IS} E_{IS}} + \alpha_{IS} \Delta T_2 \quad (6)$$

The equations for ε_{PC} , ε_{GC} and ε_{Core} follow the same form as (6)

$$F_{IS} + F_{PC} + F_{GC} + F_{Core} = 0$$

$$F_{IS} = \left(\frac{A_{SS} E_{SS}}{A_{SS} E_{SS} + A_{PC} E_{PC} + A_{GC} E_{GC}} \right) \left(A_{PC} E_{PC} (\alpha_{PC} \Delta T_4) + A_{GC} E_{GC} (\alpha_{GC} \Delta T_5) \right) - (A_{PC} E_{PC} + A_{GC} E_{GC}) (\alpha_{SS} \Delta T_2) \quad (7)$$

The equations for F_{PC} , F_{GC} and F_{Core} follow the same form as (7)

Where the symbols represent:

<i>IS</i>	Isolation Material
<i>Air</i>	Air
<i>PC</i>	Protective Coating
<i>GC</i>	Glass cladding
<i>Core</i>	Core
<i>In</i>	Inner surface
<i>Out</i>	Outer surface
<i>mid</i>	Mean
r_{Out_PC}	Radius
D_{Out_PC}	Outer diameter

The strain effects within the prepreg were determined by the superposition of the isolated and non-isolated FBG for each orientation within the prepreg laminate. (Figure 7). Thermal expansion of the resin and fibres was detected in both the 0° and 90° orientations; illustrated by an initial positive strain reading. The results show that the amount of thermal expansion strain was greater in the 90° orientation compared to the 0° orientation.

Chemical resin shrinkage was observed between 25mins and 55mins into the cure cycle in the 0° orientation to the reinforcement. Due to the difficulty faced in separating thermal expansion effects of the fibre from the resin shrinkage, it is unclear whether resin shrinkage starts 30 mins or 42 mins into the cure cycle in the 90° orientation to the reinforcement - the fibre direction of the prepreg potentially has an effect on the detection of cure shrinkage. Figure 7 shows that a significantly larger amount of resin shrinkage is detected in the 90° orientation – where the thermal expansion effects are larger. The isolated sensors have reliably detected the residual compressive strain induced after the specimen has cooled. Similar results were reported by Crosby et al. [6] by using transmission near-IR optical fiber sensor.

Figure 6 Comparison between two FBG sensors (non-isolated and isolated in a Ø0.3mm glass capillary tube) embedded into uni-directional E-glass prepreg
 (a) Parallel to the reinforced direction. (b) Perpendicular to the reinforced direction.

Figure 7 Comparison of the chemical resin shrinkage detected in the reinforced direction (90 degree) and parallel to fibre direction (0 degree) with the effects of temperature removed.

Figure 8: Comparison between the normalised experimental isolation material and the Simulink® model

The numerical model shows good agreement with the normalised experimental data. Figure 8 has the potential to be used in more complex reinforcement and temperature Figure 6 fields.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has evaluated several experimental methods of temperature isolation techniques for cure monitoring.

It was found that encasing the FBG sensors into a 0.3mm diameter glass capillary tube has the least effect on the FBG temperature detection over that of the other systems trialled. The results show successful isolation of the thermal and true strain effects at a constant temperature region of the curing cycles. Further work is needed to understand the recorded strains in the unstable cooling stage of the cure cycle.

The results showed good correlation between the Simulink model and the experimental fibres encased in the glass capillary tube.

Chemical resin shrinkage was detected in both the 0° and 90° orientations to the reinforcement during curing. A two-fold increase in detectable strain was observed when comparing the 90° orientation to the 0° orientation. This is a function of the restrictions created by the uni-directional reinforcement.

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